

BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE COLUMNS WITH GFRP REBARS UNDER ECCENTRIC COMPRESSION

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Keywords: Short columns, Eccentric compression, GFRP reinforcement, Hybrid fibres.

ABSTRACT

The corrosion of reinforcement significantly lowers the durability of steel-reinforced concrete (RC) components. In RC members, using fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) bars is a feasible alternative to steel. However, because of the linear stress-strain behaviour, brittle failure of FRP is a significant issue. Using discrete fibres in FRP RC components can improve overall performance and provide pseudo-ductility. This research investigates the behaviour of a hybrid mix of macro-synthetic poly-olefin and steel fibre reinforced (HB) RC columns with glass FRP (GFRP-RCC) rebar under eccentric compression. Sixteen RC columns with 300×300 mm cross sections were cast. Eight columns were tested at two e/d ratios of 0.2 and 0.4 to investigate column behaviour. The test matrix has (i) GFRP control columns, (ii) GFRP RCC containing 0.35% HB, (iii) GFRP RCC containing 0.70% HB, and (iv) GFRP RCC containing 1.00% HB. The research revealed that adding fibre to FRP RCC increased peak strength under eccentric axial compression. HB fibres, on the other hand, resulted in dispersed crack formation on the column tension face. Concrete spalling was prevented due to the presence of fibres that provided pseudo-ductility on the compression. To investigate column behavior, eight columns were tested at e/d ratios of 0.2 (e=60 mm), while an additional eight columns were tested at an e/d ratio of 0.4 (e=120 mm).

INTRODUCTION

Steel rebars are commonly used in reinforced concrete (RC) components. Steel rebar corrosion in RC components can significantly reduce their overall strength and stability. Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) rebars have emerged as a viable replacement for steel rebars. GFRP rebars also feature mechanical qualities such as high strength, stiffness-to-weight ratio, and corrosion resistance. The presence of electromagnetic fields does not affect on them. Many studies have previously investigated the behaviour of FRP RC components under various loadings [Afifi et al. 2014, De Luca et al. 2010, Mohamed et al. 2014]. Alsayed [Alsayed 1998] found that replacing steel reinforcement with the same area of GFRP rebars reduced load-carrying capacity by 13%, regardless of whether steel or GFRP ties were used. Square RC columns were also tested with GFRP rebars and ties [Guerin et al. 2018]. Steel and GFRP RC columns performed indistinguishably, demonstrating that GFRP rebars and ties are equally efficient as steel reinforcement in RC columns.

Elchalakani et al. (2017) and Barua et al. (2020), focused on the behaviour of FRP RC columns under eccentric compression. According to present code regulations, the capacity of FRP bars under compression is not incorporated in the design calculations of [CSA 806-2012 and ACI 440.1R-2015]. When concrete breaks at low strain, the contribution of GFRP rebars in compression is minimal. Additional study to improve the contribution of GFRP bars under compression was also emphasised [ACI 440.1R-2015]. According to recent research, BFRP-RC columns constrained with BFRP ties enhanced ultimate capacity and longitudinal rebar strength contribution. Furthermore, under eccentric compression, the confinement efficiency of BFRP ties is equivalent to that of steel tie confined columns at the same spacing [ElMessalami et al. 2020].

Fibres are added to the concrete mix to enhance crack arresting under tensile and flexural tensile stresses. Previous research [Buratti et al. 2011 and Caggiano et al. 2012] shown that adding steel fibres to concrete improves post-cracking performance and increases toughness. Steel fibres are often employed in concrete due to their remarkable mechanical qualities. Higher steel fibre addition doses, on the other hand, might induce balling effects and workability issues. [Buratti et al. 2011 and Li et al. 2012]. Furthermore, it increases the cost of FRC. A hybrid FRC (HFRC) is created by combining steel and synthetic fibres in concrete. HFRC aids in the retention of workability in the fresh condition, the improvement of mechanical properties in the hardened state, and the reduction of cost [Banthia et al. 2007 and Deng et al. 2006]. Understanding the behaviour of HFRC requires optimising the various kinds of fibres, dose, and combinations.

This study showed the findings of experimental eccentric compression testing on GFRP-reinforced columns with and without hybrid fibres (steel + polyolefin). The primary purpose of this research is to better understand the behaviour of GFRP reinforcement in columns with hybrid fibres (steel + polyolefin). FRP failure becomes brittle when used as column reinforcement due to sudden rupture after reaching ultimate strength. The contribution of fibre activity in the post-peak response under eccentric compression aids in eliminating the sudden decrease in load capacity. The secondary purpose was to investigate the load contribution of GFRP rebars in the column and the effect of fibres on the ductility of the GFRP-FRC column.

RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

The goal of this study is to gain a better understanding of the behaviour of GFRP RC columns under uniaxial eccentric compression. With the addition of hybrid (steel + synthetic) fibres, the emphasis is on increasing the performance of GFRP RC columns. Due to the brittle nature of GFRP rebars, the failure mechanism of GFRP RC columns will not be ductile. Because discrete fibres delay cracks opening, they aid in minimising sudden drops in load-carrying capacity. The crack bridging activity of the fibres gives the GFRP RC components pseudo-ductility. As a result, it is vital to explore the effect of different fibre doses on peak and post-peak behaviour enhancement caused by fibre addition. The current experimental investigation attempts to close these knowledge gaps and give new insights into the influence of fibres on the behaviour of GFRP RC columns under eccentric compression.

Table 1: Hooked end steel and poly-olefin fibre properties

Parameter	Poly-olefin (PO)	Hooked end steel fibres
Specific Gravity	0.9	7.8
Length of Fibre (mm)	50	35
Diameter of Fibre (mm)	0.5	0.7
Volume of Fibre (mm ³)	9.8	13.4
Aspect ratio (L/D)	100	50
Tensile strength (MPa)	618	1000
Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	10	200

MATERIALS

Fibres

The mechanical properties of steel and macro-synthetic polyolefin fibres used in this study are shown in Table 1. Polyolefin (PO) fibres with an aspect ratio of 100 were used, as was hooked-end steel fibre with an aspect ratio of 50. During production, grooves were carved into the PO fibres to improve their bond with the concrete. The density of the fibres, according to the manufacturer, is 910 kg/m³. During FRC preparation, this value was used to determine fibre weight from volume fraction (V_f). Two types of fibres combine to make workable concrete with a synergistic impact on crack bridging.

Concrete

The target compressive strength of the concrete mix was set at 25 MPa. The components used to make the mix (in kg/m³) are cement (305), coarse aggregate (1190), fine aggregate (760), water (153) and additive (3.6). The use of fibres has a significant impact on the workability of concrete. To improve workability, 1% sulpho-naphthalene-based superplasticizer (Glenium B233) was added to the concrete mix. To help in the hydration process, the cast concrete members were water cured for 28 days. Standard-sized cylinders were also prepared along with columns to evaluate the compressive strength of concrete under compression. The authors previously investigated cylinders under displacement-controlled mode of loading to analyse the stress-strain response under uniaxial compression. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the stress-strain response of hybrid fibres to that of a control cylinder. Previously, [Patil et al. 2020 and Patil et al. 2021] studied two types of fibres: one made entirely of PO fibres and another made entirely of PO and steel fibres (Hybrid FRC). As shown in Figure 1, failure strain increased as V_f increased. According to the stress-strain behaviour, adding fibres assists in achieving a post-peak response with higher peak strength for Normal strength concrete (NSC) of the same mix used in this study. Similarly, an increase in strength can be observed in the compression test results presented in Table 2.

Figure 1: FRC post-peak behaviour under compression for HFRC and NSC

Table 2: Concrete cylinder compressive strength

Specimen	Volume of fibres (V_f) (%)	Average Compressive Strength (MPa) ' f_c '	Standard deviation of compressive strength (MPa)	Average Ultimate Strain (30% drop from peak load)	Standard deviation of ultimate strain
Control	0.00	27.1	0.89	0.0022	0.00075
HB35	0.35	30.3	1.13	0.0043	0.00089
HB70	0.70	31.6	0.72	0.0051	0.00156
HB100	1.00	33.4	0.84	0.0065	0.00133

Reinforcement

GFRP rebars and stirrups were used for internal reinforcement in all the columns. Three specimens were tested under tension according to ASTM 7205 [ASTM 7205-2006] and under compression by using Khorramian & Sadeghian [Khorramian et al. 2019] testing procedure for GFRP rebars. Figure 2 depicts the rebars used in the specimens in further detail. Tensile strength and elastic modulus are 848 MPa and 53.5 GPa, respectively (Figure. 2). GFRP rebars of 12 mm diameter are used as longitudinal reinforcement in all specimens, with a reinforcement ratio of 1.5%. Stirrups were made of GFRP rebar with a 10 mm diameter and a length of 250×250 mm. under compression GFRP rebars showed average compressive strength of 570 MPa and modulus of 50 GPa. Compressive strength of GFRP was found to be 67 % as that of tensile strength.

Figure 2: Stress-strain response of GFRP rebar tested under uniaxial tension and compression

Table 3: Test matrix

Specimen ID	Type of fibre used	PO Fibre content (V_f)	Area of longitudinal reinforcement (mm^2)	Longitudinal reinforcement ratio ρ_l (%)	Transverse reinforcement ratio ρ_t (%)	Number of specimens LE (e/d= 0.2) (e=60 mm)	Number of specimens HE (e/d= 0.4) (e=120 mm)
Control	- -	0.00%	12 Φ 12 = 1356	1.5	0.58	2	2
HB35	Polyolef in + Steel	0.35%	12 Φ 12 = 1356	1.5	0.58	2	2
HB70		0.70%	12 Φ 12 = 1356	1.5	0.58	2	2
HB100		1.00%	12 Φ 12 = 1356	1.5	0.58	2	2

TEST MATRIX AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Sixteen full-scale square short columns with cross-sectional dimensions of 300×300 mm were tested (Table 3). The height of the column was 1100 mm, suggesting that it is a short column. The current study's test matrix was created to assess the influence of hybrid fibre reinforced concrete (HFRC) on GFRP RC column response using different fibre volume fractions. In HB35, 35 refers to the volume fraction of FRC for 0.35% fibres by the volume of concrete. Similarly, 70 represents 0.7% by the volume of concrete and 100 represents 1.0% by the total volume of concrete. Control specimens include two plain-concrete columns (P) reinforced with GFRP (Control-1 and Control-2). Two columns were assessed for individual volume % (V_f) of fibres for each eccentricity ratio (e/d), along with two control specimens without fibres. As transverse reinforcement, GFRP stirrups with dimensions of 250×250 mm and 10 mm diameter were used at a spacing of 150 mm c/c. To prevent end failure, stirrups were placed 40 mm apart near both the ends of the column over a 100 mm distance (Figure.3). Different fibres used in the FRC preparation is as shown in figure 3(c).

(a) Schematic of reinforcement (b) Reinforcement cage (c) Fibres

Figure. 3: Reinforcement details, location of Strain gauge (SG) and fibres.

INSTRUMENTATION AND TEST SETUP

Internal and exterior instruments were used to measure the column local and global strain distribution. During the reinforcement cage construction, four strain gauges were mounted on longitudinal reinforcement at mid-height of the column, one on each column face of longitudinal reinforcement. One strain gauge was mounted on a mid-height stirrup to assess strains induced by testing. Figure 1 displays the reinforcement details and strain gauge settings. Throughout the testing, four linear variable differential transducers (LVDT) were used to monitor surface deformations such as tension and compression faces. At mid-height, two lateral LVDTs were also mounted to analyse lateral deformations on both sides (compression and tension face). The data was recorded using an external data acquisition system (DAQ). To transfer the eccentric load with rollers, collar caps were placed on both ends (Figure 4(b)). While testing, using end collar caps decreases the likelihood of failure at the ends. All tests were performed on a compression testing machine (CTM) with a 3000 kN capacity. 10% preload was applied to the specimens before starting of the test to remove any possible slack.

Figure. 4: Test setup of eccentric compression test on columns. (a) Eccentric compression test setup (b) Schematic representation (side view)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Behaviour

Under a practical scenario, columns are always subjected to eccentric compression due to various imperfections in the shapes of elements and load transfer. Therefore, considering minimum eccentricity for column design is inevitable. Eight columns each were tested under low eccentricity of e/d ratio equal to 0.2 ($e=60$ mm) and high eccentricity of $e/d=0.4$ ($e=120$ mm) including NSC and FRC specimens. Various parameters such as axial deformation at peak ($\delta_{peak,LE/HE}$), peak load capacity ($P_{peak,LE/HE}$), lateral deflection at peak ($\Delta_{peak,LE/HE}$), strain in the GFRP rebars on compression side ($\epsilon_{sg,peak,LE/HE}$) and deformability index (μ_{LE}) were considered. Important results are shown in Table 4 for both low (LE) and high eccentric (HE) loading. All the specimens failed due to concrete crushing on the compression side before the horizontal tension cracks opened significantly on the tension side. Concrete crushing started at nearly 85-90 % peak load resistance in LE compression and 60-70 % peak load when tested under HE loading. Severe spalling of concrete occurred after reaching the peak load in control specimens. Cover spalling was effectively prevented by using fibres in concrete. The bridging action of fibres in FRC specimens controlled cracks widening on the tension side. However, the cracks widened significantly in control specimens soon after reaching peak capacity, leading to failure.

Under low eccentric compression, HB35 specimens showed a 17.2% increase in load-carrying capacity compared to the control specimen. For HB70 and HB100, the improvement in the load capacity was 20.1 % and 34 %, respectively. HB fibres showed significant improvement in the load-carrying capacity compared to control column under LE. Figure 5(a) Shows the load-axial deformation behaviour under LE loading. Compared with control specimens tested under high eccentricity, HB35 had a 22% increase in strength. The improvement in load for HE specimens was higher than LE specimens when compared with their respective control specimens. The average capacity of HB70 and HB100 columns increased by 32 % and 40%, respectively, compared to control columns tested under high eccentricity (HE) (Figure 5(b)). As shown in table 4.

Strain in GFRP rebars under eccentric load

Strain data of longitudinal rebars on compression and tension side was acquired from the strain gauges. Strain in GFRP rebars on the compression side at peak ($\epsilon_{sg,peak}$) is considered to understand the rebars contribution in load resistance under eccentric compression (Table 4). An increase in axial load was observed due to a delay in concrete failure on compression side in both the LE and HE cases. Strain in GFRP rebar increased with the addition of fibres when compared with control specimen on the

compression side. Addition of fibres in concrete improved the performance of GFRP on the compression side and reduced the strain in GFRP on the tension side. Reduction in the rebar strain on the tension side is due to fibres contribution in resisting cracks which reduced rebar stress. However, columns with hybrid fibres performed better than the control ones.

Deformability Index

Ductility of structural elements can be measured in terms of rotation, axial deformation, curvature, strain, absorbed energy, or dissipated energy [Bakouregui et al. 2020]. The ductility of the tested columns were measured through energy absorption as per the following equation

$$\mu = \frac{A_{885}}{A_{875}} = \frac{\text{Area OBC}}{\text{Area OAD}} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

Figure 6 shows that A_{75} is the area under the axial load-deflection curve up to 75% (Area OAD). Number 75 in A_{75} is the value of the specimen's axial deflection in the elastic region of the load-deflection curve corresponding to 75% of the peak load. The area under the axial load-deflection curve up to 85% of the peak load in post-peak is known as A_{85} (Area OBC). In the post-ultimate collapse curve of the load deflection, 85% of the peak load corresponds to the axial deflection of the columns. In general μ is calculated using eq 1. Table 4 shows the computed deformability index for low and high eccentric loads as μ_{LE} and μ_{HE} , respectively. Under low eccentric loading, the average value of μ_{LE} in the control specimen was only two. Pseudo-ductility (μ_{LE}) for HB35, HB70, and HB100 specimens were 2.66, 3.18 and 3.38, respectively as shown in table 4. HB specimens with an increase in dosages of fibres pseudo-ductility showed increase.

Under high eccentricity, the Psuedo-ductility/deformability index (μ_{HE}) for control specimen was found to be 2.22. For HB specimens under HE with 0.35, 0.7 and 1 % fibres, μ_{HE} is 2.37, 2.68 and 2.89, respectively as shown in Table 4. Under 0.4 eccentricity, all the HB specimens showed higher deformability index than the control specimen. Because of their high elastic modulus, steel fibres enhanced post-peak ductility in HB specimens, which aided in efficient and quick crack arresting after the first cracking. Fibre bridging prevented the concrete cover spalling. Fibres assisted in exerting passive pressure in FRC, enhancing the strength and ductility of FRC columns. As the stress decreases, microcracks in FRC columns join together to form a macro crack. Similar failure mode was observed in both the control specimens, with concrete crushing through a steady progression of horizontal fissures on the tension side shortly after reaching the peak stress in LE. The crack bridging of fibres prevented concrete cover spalling completely in columns with 0.7 and 1% fibres. As a result of the fracture bridging effect of macro fibres during eccentric compression, FRC specimens exhibited excellent integrity.

Table 4: Summary of test findings for tested specimens under eccentric compression

Specimen ID	Peak load LE (kN)	$\delta_{peak, LE}$ (mm)	$\Delta_{peak, LE}$ (mm)	Peak load HE (kN)	$\delta_{peak, HE}$ (mm)	$\Delta_{peak, HE}$ (mm)	$E_{sg, peak, LE}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	$E_{sg, peak, HE}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	Ductility (μ_{LE})	Ductility (μ_{HE})
Control-1	1257	4.35	2.14	792	5.03	4.35	320	2098	2.00	2.22
Control-2	1452			795						
HB35-1	1587	5.72	2.04	933	5.73	4.12	1437	2758	2.66*	2.37
HB35-2	--			995						
HB70-1	1682	6.01	2.13	1110	6.55	4.89	3048	2171**	3.18	2.68
HB70-2	1566			1035						
HB100-1	1814	6.23	2.35	1155	6.70	--	3723	4551	3.38*	2.89
HB100-2	--			1055		5.43				

Note:1. HB35-2 and HB100-2 columns data was lost due to technical error during testing.

2. The ductility given by $\mu = \frac{A_{885}}{A_{875}}$ shown in Figure. 6

3. * mark indicates only one specimen data is taken for calculating μ . ** indicates strain gauge malfunctioned before peak load

a) LE compression

b) HE compression

Figure 5: Load-Axial deformation behaviour of columns under eccentric load

Figure 6: Ductility of GFRP RC column under eccentricity

Mode of Failures in GFRP FRC Columns under Eccentric Compression

All the columns studied to failed by concrete crushing on compression side without GFRP rebar rupture on tension side. Column failure modes were same under both low and high eccentric loads, i.e., LE and HE specimens. Columns subjected to HE tests, on the other hand, revealed concrete crushing on the compression side is more and larger cracks on the tension side due to higher bending loads than LE case. Control columns exhibited a sharp drop in load capacity quickly after reaching peak load. HFRC columns showed higher pseudo-ductility value before the complete failure of columns. Cover concrete spalling was only found in control columns, while FRC columns with no spalling were unaffected. Cracks were more distributed on the tension side with an increase in the dosage of fibres (higher V_f), the same can be observed in Figure 7. Buckling of longitudinal rebars was observed in the control specimen due to spalling of cover concrete soon after the peak load was reached. Figure 7 also shows the compression side failure of columns (Right side image) due to concrete crushing. Lateral stability of rebars in compression drops suddenly with concrete spalling, resulting in rebar buckling (Fig. 7(a)). There was no buckling in the case of FRC columns, as there was no spalling of concrete.

Figure 7: Failure modes of GFRP-FRC column under eccentric compression side view and compression face.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the effectiveness of Fibre reinforced concrete (FRC) in improving the performance of GFRP reinforced concrete columns under eccentric axial compression. The following important conclusions can be drawn from this study:

- Applied eccentricity ratios strongly impacted the strength, failure, and behaviour of GFRP RC column elements with and without fibres. As eccentricity increased, axial capacity decreased. All the tested columns failed due to concrete crushing on the compression side.
- The addition of fibres helped in improving the strength, pseudo-ductility, and post-peak capacity of GFRP RC columns. Deformability increased with an increase in fibre dosage.
- GFRP rebars buckled under low and high eccentricity after the spalling of cover concrete on the compression side in control specimens. The concrete cover spalling was effectively prevented by fibre addition which prevented the buckling of rebars.
- The sudden drop in compression load resistance was prevented at higher dosages of HB (0.7% and 1.0%). Due to improved crack arresting with fibre addition, deformability improved in the specimens tested at low and high eccentric compression.
- Fibres helped in terms of two major contributions. With increase in the volume of fibres, improvement in compressive strength was observed. They also improved the peak strain ($\epsilon_{sg, peak}$) carried by GFRP rebar. Similar trend of greater improvement in $\epsilon_{sg, peak}$ is observed when fibre dosage is increased in both columns tested under eccentric compression.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude to CSK Technologies in Hyderabad for contributing the GFRP rebars used in this study. In addition, the first author is grateful for the scholarship offered by the Ministry of Education (MOE) of the Government of India. Greenix Infra Limited provided the Macro Synthetic Fibres. Their assistance is also appreciated.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.